

THE USE OF METADISOURSE MARKERS IN L2 TURKISH OPINION TEXTS BY NATIVE ALBANIAN STUDENTS

Research Article

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Abstract: Metadiscourse is widely recognized as a fundamental rhetorical device in discourse construction, playing a key role in organizing and shaping persuasive texts, especially in the context of second language (L2) learning and teaching. In recent years, notable progress has been made in studies on metadiscourse in teaching Turkish as a second language. However, research on metadiscourse use in various L2 contexts, particularly in academic and opinion-based writing, remains limited. This study investigates the use of metadiscourse in opinion texts written by Albanian students learning Turkish as a second language, employing Hyland's Interpersonal Model of Metadiscourse as the analytical framework. Employing AntConc 4.2.0 for corpus analysis and Log-likelihood statistics, the study reveals that native Albanian students frequently use metadiscourse markers in their L2 texts to present their opinions within an organized discourse and engage readers throughout the text, with a notable inclination to use interactional elements. Transitions and self-mentions are the most commonly used metadiscourse categories, indicating students' efforts to maintain a logical flow and personal engagement in their texts. However, the relatively lower use of evidentials and endophoric markers suggests a need for greater emphasis on these elements to enhance the quality of academic writing. The results are expected to help syllabus designers and educators develop specialized pedagogical strategies to improve students' academic writing and communication skills in Turkish.

Keywords: Interactional categories, interactive categories, L2 Turkish opinion texts, metadiscourse, native Albanian students.

ANA DİLİ ARNAVUTÇA OLAN ÖĞRENCİLER TARAFINDAN YAZILAN D2 TÜRKÇE GÖRÜŞ METİNLERİNDE ÜSTSÖYLEM BELİRLEYİCİLERİNİN KULLANIMI

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Özet: Üstsöylem, söylem oluşturma sürecinde temel bir retorik araç olarak yaygın biçimde kabul edilmekte ve özellikle ikinci dil (D2) öğretimi ile öğrenimi bağlamında ikna edici metinlerin düzenlenmesi ve şekillendirilmesinde önemli bir rol oynamaktadır. Son yıllarda, ikinci dil olarak Türkçe öğretiminde üstsöylem çalışmaları önemli ilerleme kaydetmiştir. Ancak, özellikle akademik ve görüş yazıları gibi farklı D2 bağlamlarında üstsöylem kullanımına dair araştırmalar hâlâ sınırlıdır. Hyland'ın Kişilerarası Üstsöylem Modelini çözümsel çerçeve olarak kullanan bu çalışma, Türkçeyi ikinci dil olarak öğrenen Arnavut öğrencilerin yazdığı metinlerde üstsöylem kullanımını incelemektedir. Çalışmada, metin çözümlemesi için AntConc 4.2.0 ve Log-olabilirlik istatistiği kullanılmıştır. Veri çözümlemesi, ana dili Arnavutça olan öğrencilerin ikinci dil olarak Türkçede yazdıkları metinlerde üstsöylem unsurlarını ve görüşlerini düzenli bir söylem çerçevesinde ortaya koymak ve okuyucuyla metin boyunca etkileşim kurmak için sıklıkla kullandıklarını; özellikle alıcı odaklı etkileşimli unsurları kullanmaya eğilimli olduklarını göstermektedir. Mantıksal bağlayıcılar ve kendinden söz etme unsurları, öğrencilerin metinlerinde mantıklı bir akış sağlama ve kişisel etkileşimi sürdürme çabalarını yansıtan en yaygın üstsöylem ulamları olarak belirlenmiştir. Öte yandan, tanıtlayıcı ve metin içi belirleyicilerin daha az kullanılması, akademik yazının niteliğini geliştirmek için bu belirleyicilere daha fazla vurgu yapılması gerektiğini göstermektedir. Elde edilen sonuçların, müfredat geliştiricilere ve öğretmenlere, öğrencilerin akademik yazma becerilerini ve Türkçedeki genel iletişim yeterliklerini destekleyecek özelleştirilmiş pedagojik stratejiler geliştirmede rehberlik etmesi beklenmektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Alıcı odaklı etkileşimli ulamlar, ana dili Arnavutça olan öğrenciler, bilgi odaklı etkileşimli ulamlar, D2 Türkçe görüş metinleri, üstsöylem.

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Introduction

Metadiscourse is an essential linguistic element that helps readers understand a text, ensuring clarity and coherence. Researchers have described it in diverse ways, focusing on different aspects of its communicative function.

According to Dahl (2004, p. 1811), metadiscourse signifies “the writer’s acknowledgement of the reader”, emphasizing its role in establishing a connection between the writer and the audience. Vande Kopple (2012, p. 37) describes it as “metatalk or metacommunication”, highlighting the writer’s observations or reflections regarding their writing. Ädel (2006, p. 2) defines metadiscourse as “discourse about the evolving discourse or the writer’s explicit commentary on his/her ongoing text”, which underlines its dynamic and self-reflective characteristics. Bunton (1999, p. 27) characterizes metadiscourse as “references to the writer’s awareness in structuring the text to help readers grasp its intended organization”, highlighting its significance in textual design. Likewise, Hyland (2000, p. 109) refers to metadiscourse as “linguistic tools used to arrange discourse or express the writer’s perspective on its content or audience”, noting its organizational and evaluative aspects. In addition, Hyland (1996) recognizes metadiscourse as an essential rhetorical element in persuasive writing, underscoring its power to sway and persuade the audience. These varying definitions reveal that while scholars agree on metadiscourse’s role in structuring and directing the text, they differ in their focus on elements such as relationship-building, self-awareness, organization, and persuasion.

Overall, metadiscourse markers (MDMs) serve as tools that facilitate interaction between writers and readers in academic discourse (Hyland & Tse, 2004). They are crucial for making academic texts more accessible to readers and are recognized for enhancing the overall quality of scholarly writing (Karimi et al., 2017). MDMs guide readers through the logical structure of the text, signalling relationships between ideas and establishing a meaningful connection between the writer and the reader. With the effective use of metadiscourse markers, the quality of academic texts can be improved (Letsoela, 2014).

Metadiscourse has been classified by various scholars, including Williams (1982), Dafouz-Milne (2003), Hyland (2005), Mauranen (1993), Hyland and Tse (2004), and Ädel (2006, 2010), which enhances our understanding of its role in texts. Notably, Hyland’s (2005) taxonomy of metadiscourse is widely recognized as one of the most comprehensive and reliable frameworks in the field (Alavinia & Zarza, 2016; Ebrahimi, 2018). It categorizes metadiscourse into two main dimensions: interactive and interactional. Table 1 presents Hyland’s model, providing explanations and illustrative examples for each subcategory.

Table 1

Hyland’s Interpersonal Model of Metadiscourse (Hyland, 2005, p. 49)

Category	Function	Example
Interactive	Help to guide the reader through the text	
Transitions	Express semantic relation between main clauses	And, in addition, but, consequently
Frame markers	Refer to discourse acts, sequences, or text stages	Finally, to conclude, my purpose is
Endophoric markers	Refer to information in other parts of the text	Noted above, see Fig., in Section 2

Evidentials	Refer to source of information from other texts	According to X, (Y, 1990), Z states
Code-glosses	Help readers grasp the meanings of ideational material	Namely, e.g., such as, in other words
Interactional	Involve the reader in the text	Resources
Hedges	Withhold the writer's full commitment to the proposition	Might, perhaps, possible, about
Boosters	Emphasize force or writer's certainty in proposition in fact / definitely / it is clear that	In fact, definitely, it is clear that
Attitude Markers	Express writer's attitude to pro-position	Unfortunately, I agree, surprisingly
Engagement Markers	Explicitly refer to or build a relationship with the reader	Consider, note that, you can see that
Self-Mentions	Explicit reference to author(s)	I, we, my, our

As shown in Table 1, interactive MDMs such as transitions, frame markers, endophoric markers, evidentials, and code-glosses facilitate writer-reader interaction by guiding readers through the logical flow of arguments and providing evidence to support claims. On the other hand, interactional MDMs, including hedges, boosters, attitude markers, engagement markers, and self-mentions, establish the writer's stance, engage the reader, and soften the certainty of assertions.

The use of these MDMs spans various academic contexts, including research articles (e.g., Çapar, 2014; Eghtesadi & Navidinia, 2009), book reviews (e.g., Junqueira & Cortes, 2014), student writing (e.g., Akbaş, 2014; Lee & Deakin, 2016), textbooks (e.g., Bogdanović, 2014; Guziurová, 2017), master's theses (e.g., Ozdemir & Longo, 2014; Soyşekerçi et al., 2022), and doctoral dissertations (e.g., Kondowe, 2014; Köroğlu, 2018).

Over the past decade, research on metadiscourse analysis in second language (L2) academic writing has increased (e.g., Bax et al., 2019; Burneikaitė, 2008; Castillo-Hajan et al., 2019; Hawkey & Barker, 2004). Hyland (2000) emphasized the value of using metadiscourse (MD) in L2 writing for several reasons: it provides context, enhances persuasiveness, improves retention, increases clarity and coherence, educates readers on subjective truth interpretation, and reveals the writer's attitude. Thus, understanding metadiscourse in academic writing presents specific challenges for learners of a second language, but is crucial for achieving clarity and coherence in their writing. The studies conducted by Cubukcu (2017), Lee and Deakin (2016), and Simin and Tavangar (2009) demonstrate that successful essays often include more MD markers, suggesting a link between these markers and the writing performance of ESL students. Similarly, Intaraprawat and Steffensen (1995) examined metadiscourse in persuasive essays written by ESL university students and found that the better essays employed a broader range of metadiscourse features within each category compared to the weaker essays. The authors suggest that proficient writers recognize their readers' needs and adeptly apply strategies to enhance the accessibility and consideration of their texts. These studies consistently emphasize the role of metadiscourse in improving L2 academic writing and identifying areas for ESL writers' development.

Regarding the L2 Turkish context, previous studies primarily focused on grammatical accuracy, coherence, cohesion, and structural organization in student writing across various academic levels and topics (e.g., Ak Başoğlu & Can, 2014; Bayrakdar & Dilidüzgün, 2024; Boylu et al., 2017; Çerçi et al., 2016; Demiriz & Okur, 2019; Güler & Eyüp, 2016;

Kartallıoğlu & Topuzkanamış, 2021; Seyedi, 2019; Yağmur Şahin et al., 2013). Few studies have explored the use of MDMs in L2 Turkish texts (e.g., Esmer, 2018; Kurudayıoğlu & Çimen, 2020). Esmer (2018) analyzed 30 argumentative persuasive texts written by foreign students studying at the Mersin University Turkish Application and Research Center at B2 and C1 proficiency levels on various topics. The findings revealed that students learning Turkish as a foreign language were unable to effectively use metadiscourse markers in their texts, which hindered their ability to produce well-structured persuasive writing. Similarly, Kurudayıoğlu and Çimen (2020) investigated the use of metadiscourse in the abstracts of 20 students who had taken an Academic Turkish course at the B2 level. Their study showed that the students were unable to use interactive metadiscourse markers effectively in their abstracts. These studies demonstrate that students learning Turkish as a foreign language struggle to effectively use metadiscourse markers in their texts, which affects their ability to produce well-structured and coherent academic writing. Despite their valuable contributions to the literature, a significant gap in research remains concerning a comprehensive analysis of MDMs that covers all items within the main categories and subcategories in L2 Turkish student writing, both qualitatively and quantitatively. This gap is especially noticeable in research on foreign students learning Turkish who share the same native language. In this regard, the present study will also contribute to the literature by investigating L2 Turkish texts written by native Albanian speakers.

1. Aim of the Study

This study investigates how Albanian learners of Turkish use MDMs in their opinion texts, focusing on interactive categories such as transitions, frame markers, endophoric markers, evidentials, and code-glosses, as well as interactional categories including hedges, boosters, attitude markers, self-mentions, and engagement markers.

Through an in-depth analysis of all the main and sub-categories of the MDMs, the researcher aims to shed light on the role of MDMs in academic writing proficiency and raise awareness of their essential importance in language teaching. The research questions examined in this study are:

1. What are the metadiscourse markers and their frequencies in L2 Turkish opinion texts written by native Albanian students?
2. Is there a statistically significant difference in the overall frequency of interactive and interactional metadiscourse markers in L2 Turkish opinion texts written by native Albanian students?

This article is structured as follows: Section 2 outlines the methodology employed in the study, detailing the participants, materials, data collection procedures, and data analysis methods. Section 3 presents the findings and discussion concerning the occurrences and frequencies of metadiscursive items within the corpus. It also includes a comparative analysis of the overall use of interactive and interactional categories. The final section provides concluding remarks, discussing areas for improvement and the implications of the

findings to enhance the teaching and learning of academic Turkish writing, with a focus on metadiscourse instruction and practical strategies.

2. Research Methodology

2.1. Participants

The study involved 30 native Albanian university students aged between 20 and 28 years from the Department of Turkology at the University of Prishtina in Kosovo. They are enrolled in the Language Center within the Faculty of Philology, where they study Turkish at proficiency levels B2 and C1.

2.2. Materials

This study examined thirty opinion texts written by students who were required to compose a text of at least 170 words on the topic, “If you were to give a message to the world, what would it be?” within approximately 90 minutes. The topic was selected based on the teachers’ expert opinions.

The rationale for selecting an opinion text as the model of exposition lies in its widespread use in various educational contexts, as it serves as a traditional structure that allows for the clear articulation of arguments and viewpoints. More specifically, opinion texts exhibit distinct genre properties in which the writer conveys their thoughts, beliefs, or feelings on particular subjects, often supported by reasons and evidence to persuade readers and engage with the audience while addressing opposing viewpoints and using linking words (Ingebrand, 2016). These properties make them an ideal context for studying metadiscourse, as they naturally promote the effective application of such strategies.

2.3. Data Collection

At the end of the 2024-2025 academic year, data were collected using a non-random sampling approach, specifically through availability sampling. During this process, the researcher received support from the students’ Turkish language instructor in identifying and recruiting participants for the study, taking into account their availability and suitability. Before their involvement, all participants provided voluntary, informed consent, ensuring their willingness to participate in the research. Additionally, this study has been approved by the Ethical Committee of Social and Human Sciences Research and Publication Ethics at Gaziantep University (Gaziantep University Rectorate, Date: 04.11.2024, Meeting no:18).

2.4. Data Analysis

This study employs a mixed-methods approach, integrating qualitative and quantitative methodologies to examine metadiscourse in L2 Turkish opinion texts written by Albanian students, comprising a total of 4,568 words.

The analysis begins with a qualitative investigation, concentrating on identifying metadiscourse markers based on the contextual rhetorical functions underlying their usage, utilizing AntConc 4.2.0 software and manual analysis. To systematically identify and categorize MDMs, Hyland’s (2005) Interpersonal Model of Metadiscourse was employed as the analytical framework. This model includes interactive markers such as transitions, frame

markers, endophoric markers, evidential markers, code glosses, and interactional markers, which consist of hedges, boosters, attitude markers, self-mentions, and engagement markers (see Table 1 for details).

This is followed by a quantitative examination to explore the frequency and distribution of each metadiscourse item across its categories. Additionally, the researcher used Log-likelihood statistics to compare the overall use of interactive and interactional categories to determine whether the difference is statistically significant.

All the texts collected were included in the data analysis because they were relevant to the topic. However, texts with misspellings (e.g., *gerçekten* “really” instead of *gerçeklen-*, incorrect form), subject-verb agreement errors (e.g., *düşünüyoruz* “we are thinking” instead of *düşünüyorum* “I am thinking”), or pronoun usage mistakes (e.g., *öylece* “in that way” instead of *böylece* “thus”) were excluded from the analysis. Such errors could lead to misclassification in the metadiscourse analysis, which relies on specific categories. To ensure analytical precision, only responses that were grammatically correct in Turkish and contextually appropriate were included. Although these errors may seem as unintentional mistakes rather than a lack of grammatical knowledge, the researcher analyzed the texts without making interpretations based on their writing style.

3. Findings and Discussion

This section consists of two main parts, each addressing the research questions in order. To answer the first research question, the following section provides a detailed analysis of metadiscourse usage in Albanian students’ L2 Turkish opinion texts, presenting occurrences of each metadiscourse category ordered from the most frequently used to the least. This thorough overview examines how these students employ various MDMs to structure their arguments and engage with their audience. By assessing the frequencies and applications of these markers, the discussion uncovers insights into the students’ writing practices, demonstrating their strengths and areas for improvement in their metadiscourse strategies.

3.1. The use of MDMs in L2 Turkish Student Opinion Texts

In a dataset of 30 opinion texts authored by Albanian learners of Turkish, 722 MDMs were identified within a total of 4,568 words. This corresponds to a frequency of about 0.16 MDMs per word, meaning that one metadiscourse marker appears every 6.37 words and accounts for roughly 15,8% of the total words., highlighting their important role in guiding readers and fostering writer-reader interaction in academic writing.

Data analysis revealed that all interactional categories, such as hedges, boosters, attitude markers, engagement markers, and self-mentions, along with nearly all interactive categories, including transitions, frame markers, endophoric markers, evidentials, and code-glosses, were present in the texts. Figure 1 displays the distribution of all metadiscourse categories in the corpus.

Figure 1

The Distribution of Interactive and Interactional Subcategories in the Overall Corpus

Figure 1, which displays metadiscourse categories in the writings of L2 Turkish students by Albanians, reveals distinct patterns in both interactive and interactional categories. Self-mentions are the most common interactional category, making up 26,49% of the total. This emphasizes students' strong tendency to share personal insights and to be present in their writing. Following this, attitude markers and boosters represent 17,99% and 13,94%, respectively, indicating that students aim to express their attitudes and support their arguments. On the other hand, the use of hedges and engagement markers within the corpus is lower, at 6,27% and 8,92%, yet they still help to improve the overall interactive quality of students' writing.

The analysis shows that transitions are the most common interactive markers, appearing at a rate of 21,05%, which suggests students' attempts to improve text coherence. Conversely, frame markers and code glosses are used less frequently, with evidentials showing the lowest occurrence among these categories. Additionally, it was observed that endophoric markers were absent from the students' writing. This might indicate that students either find it difficult to include these markers effectively, do not prioritise explicit textual organisation in their writing, or that this could be entirely due to genre features. Below, all instances of each interactive and interactional category identified in the corpus will be presented and discussed, along with possible reasons for the differing frequencies of each category, listed in descending order, starting with the interactional categories.

3.1.1. Self-mentions

In L2 Turkish student writing, self-mentions are the most commonly used interactional markers, revealing the distinct voice and involvement of Albanian students. This dominance

suggests that students are largely inclined to assert their identity and engagement in their writing, occurring at a rate of approximately 26.49 per 100 words across the entire corpus of metadiscourse. As shown in Table 2, self-mentions appeared in various forms, including first-person singular suffixes, pronouns, and conditionals, reflecting the students' proficiency in the Turkish language. Below is the list of self-mentions identified in the corpus.

Table 2
Frequency and Percentages of Self-mentions in L2 Turkish Opinion Texts

Self-mentions	Frequency	Percentage (%)
-(I)m, first-person singular verbal suffix (e.g. <i>istemiyorum</i> "I don't want")	82	43,16
-(I)m, first-person singular possessive suffix (e.g. <i>hedeflerim</i> "my aims")	51	26,83
-(I)m, first-person singular suffix with subordinating suffixes and possessive suffixes (e.g. <i>yaptığım</i> "what I did")	19	9,99
first-person singular pronoun, <i>ben</i> "I"	8	4,21
-(I)m, first-person singular possessive suffix (e.g. <i>kendimi</i> "myself")	4	2,11
first-person singular possessive pronoun, <i>benim</i> "my."	4	2,11
first-person singular verbal suffix with subordinating suffix (e.g. <i>büyüdüğümde</i> "when I grow up")	4	2,11
-(I)m, first-person singular nominal suffix (e.g. <i>insanım</i> "I am a person")	3	1,58
first-person singular conditional (e.g. <i>olsam</i> "if I were")	3	1,58
first-person singular reflexive pronoun with nominative case suffix, <i>kendi</i> "own"	3	1,58
first-person singular pronoun with accusative case suffix, <i>beni</i> "me"	3	1,58
first-person singular reflexive pronoun with dative case suffix, <i>kendime</i> "to myself"	2	1,05
first-person singular verbal suffix with the subordinating conjunction (e.g. <i>-diğim için</i> "because I did")	2	1,05
first-person singular pronoun with dative case suffix, <i>bana</i> "to me"	1	0,53
-(I)m, first-person singular possessive suffix with dative case suffix (e.g. <i>aklıma</i> "to my mind")	1	0,53
Total	190	100,00

As Table 2 reveals, Albanian students frequently used various forms of self-mention in their L2 Turkish texts. The frequent use of self-mentions, along with their diverse forms, suggests that students express their opinions personally and write their texts in accordance with the genre.

The most frequently used marker is the first-person singular verbal suffix *-(I)m*, found in phrases such as *istemiyorum* "I don't want", which appears 82 times, accounting for 43,16% of the total. This indicates a strong focus on personal voice and the writer's active presence in the text. Following this, the first-person singular possessive suffix *-(I)m*, found in examples such as *hedeflerim* "my aims" and *kendimi* "myself", is prominent, with 51 occurrences, representing 26,83% of the total. This emphasizes the students' tendency to express ownership or personal connection, reflecting their relationship to their goals and themselves. The first-person singular pronoun *ben* "I" appears 8 times, constituting 4,21% of the total, showing direct self-reference without any suffix. Other forms, such as *yaptığım* "what I did" and *bildiğim* "what I know", use the *-(I)m* suffix to convey specific actions or knowledge, accounting for 9,99% and 2,11%, respectively. Markers like *büyüdüğümde* "when I grow up"

and *-diğim için* “because I did” appear less frequently, contributing 2,11% and 1,05% to the total. These forms reflect various contexts but are relatively minor in the texts. Below is an example of self-mention in the first-person singular with a conditional suffix, extracted from the corpus.

- (1) *Bütün dünyaya bir mesaj verecek olsam hayallerinizden vazgeçmeyin olurdu.* “If I were to give a message to the whole world, it would be ‘Do not give up on your dreams.’”

In the example above, the self-mention reflects the speaker’s influence and authority over the message. It indicates that the advice is not merely a generic statement, but rather something in which the speaker is personally engaged and wishes to share with the audience.

In Turkish, an agglutinative language, personal suffixes like *-Im* “I” and *-Iz* “we” are integral to verbs. Although Albanian is less agglutinative, it also employs personal suffixes such as *-j* “I” and *-jmë* “we”, which similarly influence the frequency of self-mentions (Camaj, 1984; Koleci & Turano, 2011). Accordingly, it can be asserted that the morphological features of the Turkish language facilitate the seamless integration of self-mentions, while the suffixes of Albanian contribute to self-mentions, although to a lesser extent.

Another possible reason for the high use of self-mentions could be attributed to genre properties, considering that opinion texts present the writer’s viewpoint on a topic and aim to persuade the reader to agree by supporting their opinions (Oshima & Hogue, 1988). Hyland (2008) also found that self-mentions are prevalent in student writing, indicating the writer’s engagement with the material. This argument may also explain why Albanian students employed self-mentions only to refer to themselves explicitly, as shown in Table 2. Although they have learnt to use passive construction in Turkish, the students did not include any implicit self-reference in their texts. This could arise from the opinion text genre promoting clear personal engagement or the influence of cultural preferences.

3.1.2. Attitude Markers

Albanian students frequently use attitude markers to express their stances and evaluative judgments. Their significant presence indicates that students often signal their evaluative stance, which can enhance engagement and clarity. Nevertheless, the excessive use of attitude markers may create a subjective tone that could detract from objectivity. By maintaining this balance, Albanian students can effectively employ attitude markers in their writing while preserving their academic rigour and persuasive power. Swales and Feak (2004) note that attitude markers are instrumental in conveying the writer’s opinions and stance, which is essential for engaging readers and establishing an authorial voice.

As Table 3 presents, the students expressed their subjective viewpoints and personal attitudes on the content through various realizations of attitude markers, such as attitudinal adjectives (e.g., *mükemmel* “perfect”), attitudinal verbs (e.g., *çabala-* “to strive”), attitudinal adverbs (e.g., *iyi şekilde* “in a good way”), and attitudinal nouns (e.g., *zorluk* “difficulty”). Below are all the occurrences of attitude markers in the corpus with their frequencies and percentages, listed from most to least frequently used.

Table 3
Frequency and Percentages of Attitude Markers in L2 Turkish Opinion Texts

Attitude Markers	Frequency	Percentage (%)
<i>iste-</i> “to want”	52	39,40
<i>inanılmaz</i> “unbelievable”	9	6,82
<i>mükemmel</i> “perfect”	8	6,06
<i>-maya çalış-</i> “to try to”	6	4,54
<i>önemli</i> “important”	5	3,78
<i>zorluk</i> “difficulty”	5	3,78
<i>büyük</i> “big”	4	3,03
<i>akılda kalıcı</i> “catchy”	3	2,27
<i>kolay</i> “easy”	3	2,27
<i>ilginç</i> “interesting”	3	2,27
<i>küçük</i> “small”	2	1,51
<i>güçlü</i> “strong”	2	1,51
<i>bence</i> “in my opinion”	2	1,51
<i>merak et-</i> “to be curious about”	2	1,51
<i>mutlu ol</i> “to get happy”	2	1,51
<i>değerli</i> “precious”	2	1,51
<i>mutlu</i> “happy”	1	0,76
<i>çaba harca-</i> “to make an effort”	1	0,76
<i>gelişigüzel</i> “random”	1	0,76
<i>güzellik</i> “beauty”	1	0,76
<i>güzel</i> “beautiful”	1	0,76
<i>en azından</i> “at least”	1	0,76
<i>kötü</i> “bad”	1	0,76
<i>unutulmaz</i> “unforgettable”	1	0,76
<i>duygusal</i> “sentimental”	1	0,76
<i>-dan etkilen-</i> “to be affected by...”	1	0,76
<i>çabala-</i> “to strive”	1	0,76
<i>yeterli</i> “sufficient”	1	0,76
<i>inşallah</i> “hopefully”	1	0,76
<i>zorlu</i> “tough”	1	0,76
<i>maalesef</i> “unfortunately”	1	0,76
<i>iyi şekilde</i> “in a good way”	1	0,76
<i>komik</i> “funny”	1	0,76
<i>garip</i> “strange”	1	0,76
<i>üzücü</i> “upsetting”	1	0,76
<i>komik</i> “funny”	1	0,76
<i>garip</i> “strange”	1	0,76
<i>üzücü</i> “upsetting”	1	0,76
Total	132	100,00

Data analysis of this study reveals that attitude markers are the metadiscourse category with the most varied instances in the corpus, with 38 different occurrences, as illustrated in Table 3. This indicates that Albanian students frequently use attitude markers to express their opinions and evaluations in L2 Turkish texts. The distinct properties of each category can account for the variations in their realizations. For instance, endophoric markers, which refer to previous or following parts of the text, have more constrained means of expression than attitude markers, which offer writers a wider range of linguistic forms to convey their stance.

The verb *iste-* “to want” is notably dominant, appearing in 39,40% of attitude marker occurrences, suggesting that Albanian students rely heavily on conveying desire or intention

in their writing. This preference indicates their inclination to communicate their wishes and preferences. Evaluative adjectives such as *inanılmaz* “unbelievable” and *mükemmel* “perfect” are also frequently used, with occurrences of 6,82% and 6,06%, respectively. Their frequent use indicates a tendency to emphasize the extremity or quality of their opinions, reflecting a pattern of strong evaluative statements. In contrast, verbs such as *-maya çalış-* (“to try to”) are used moderately, appearing 4,54% of the time, showing that while efforts and actions are discussed, they are less central than evaluative terms. Below, you can see an example of an attitude marker found in the corpus.

(2) *Dünyada insanların daha nazik ve anlayışlı olmasını isterim.* “I would like people in the world to be more kind and understanding.”

The sentence (2) conveys a strong personal desire for a specific outcome through the use of *iste-* “(to) want to”, which emphasizes the student’s wish for a change in the behaviour of people in the world. Hyland (2005) argues that attitude markers pave the way for a more relatable and vivid writing style. In this regard, the attitude markers used by Albanian students in their L2 texts influence the tone and persuasiveness of their work.

3.1.3. Boosters

Data analysis reveals that boosters were frequently used in L2 Turkish texts written by native Albanian students. This may indicate a deliberate effort by the students to assert the importance and certainty of their statements.

The students also employed boosters to express certainty about their arguments, minimizing the potential for reader disagreement. This was achieved through various realizations such as universal pronouns (e.g., *her şey* “everything”), emphatics (e.g., *kesinlikle* “definitely”) and amplifiers (e.g., *hep* “always”). Table 4 presents the list of boosters used by Albanian students in their L2 Turkish opinion texts.

Table 4

Frequency and Percentages of Boosters in L2 Turkish Opinion Texts

Boosters	Frequency	Percentage (%)
<i>çok</i> “a lot”	20	21,05
<i>en</i> “the most”	19	20,00
<i>çok</i> “very”	11	11,57
<i>sadece</i> “only”	3	3,16
<i>hep</i> “always”	3	3,16
<i>bile</i> “even”	3	3,16
<i>her zaman</i> “every time”	3	3,16
<i>aslında</i> “actually”	3	3,16
<i>asla</i> “never”	2	2,11
<i>hiç</i> “none”	2	2,11
<i>o kadar ... ki</i> “so”	2	2,11
<i>hiçbir şey</i> “nothing”	2	2,11
<i>kesinlikle</i> “definitely”	2	2,11
<i>hatta</i> “even”	2	2,11
<i>tüm</i> “all”	2	2,11
<i>çok ama çok</i> “too much”	2	2,11
<i>elbette ki</i> “by all means”	1	1,05

<i>herkes</i> “everyone”	1	1,05
<i>her şey</i> “everything”	1	1,05
<i>hiç</i> “never”	1	1,05
<i>asıl</i> “principal”	1	1,05
<i>öncelikli</i> “primary”	1	1,05
<i>hiç kimse</i> “nobody”	1	1,05
<i>hiçbir zaman</i> “never”	1	1,05
<i>tabi</i> “of course”	1	1,05
<i>hele</i> “especially”	1	1,05
<i>öyle güzel</i> “so beautiful”	1	1,05
<i>ne olursa olsun</i> “whatever happens”	1	1,05
<i>her</i> “every”	1	1,05
<i>çok fazla</i> “too much”	1	1,05
Total	95	100,00

As shown in Table 4, the most common boosters are *çok* “a lot”, which appears 20 times and constitutes 21,05% of the total, and *en* “the most”, used 19 times and representing 20,00%. This may arise from their familiarity or effectiveness in expressing strong opinions, as these boosters function as amplifiers and serve as intensifiers, exaggerations, and overstatements. Moderately used boosters, such as *çok* “very”, which occurs 11 times and accounts for 11,57%, along with *sadece* “only”, *hep* “always”, *bile* “even”, *her zaman* “every time”, and *aslında* “actually”, each used 3 times and constituting 3,16%, reflect a balanced use of emphasis techniques. Less frequent boosters, including *asla* “never”, *hiç* “none”, *o kadar ... ki* “so”, *hiçbir şey* “nothing”, *kesinlikle* “definitely”, *hatta* “even”, *tüm* “all”, and *çok ama çok* “too much”, each appearing twice and making up 2,11%, show a diverse but less common use of these words.

Despite certain expressions functioning as boosters, which appear exclusively once in the entire corpus, such as *elbette ki* “by all means”, *herkes* “everyone”, *her şey* “everything” and “primary”, the use of a diverse array of boosters in the corpus illustrates proficiency in reinforcing arguments, conveying certainty, and asserting opinions with greater emphasis. Below is an example of a booster used in a sentence from L2 student texts.

(3) *Her zaman pozitif düşünmek lazım.* “One should **always** think positively.”

In example (3), *her zaman* “always” effectively amplifies the statement, emphasizing the significance and constancy of the advice. Vázquez Orta and Giner (2009) argue that boosters play a crucial role in amplifying the persuasive power of arguments. Thus, the boosters listed in Table 4 are believed to reinforce the arguments and help students convey a sense of confidence in their assertions while writing opinion text in Turkish as a second language.

3.1.4. Engagement Markers

The use of engagement markers in L2 Turkish texts indicates that Albanian students are attempting to engage the reader, consistent with Hyland’s (2005) observation that engagement markers help writers involve readers in discourse.

As Table 5 reveals, the students engage and involve readers in their writing through various realizations of engagement markers, such as inclusive we (e.g., *-(I)z*, *-(I)k*, first-person plural verbal suffixes (e.g., *...yapıyoruz* “we do ...”), reader pronoun (e.g., *-(I)n*, second-person

singular possessive suffix (e.g., *hedeflerin* “your aims”), directives (e.g., *-In(Iz)*, imperative suffix for second person plural) (e.g., *Belirleyin!* “Determine!”), and rhetorical questions (e.g., *...nelerdir?* “what are ... (they)?”). Table 5 presents the various realizations of engagement markers that Albanian students utilize in their L2 Turkish texts.

Table 5

Frequency and Percentages of Engagement Markers in L2 Turkish Opinion Texts

Engagement Markers	Frequency	Percentage (%)
<i>-(I)z, -(I)k</i> , first-person plural verbal suffixes (e.g. <i>...yapıyoruz</i> “we do ...”)	15	20,84
<i>-(I)mIz</i> , first-person plural possessive suffixes (e.g. <i>hayallerimiz</i> “our dreams”)	12	16,67
<i>-(I)n</i> , second-person singular possessive suffix (e.g. <i>hedeflerin</i> “your aims”)	10	13,89
<i>-(I)n</i> , second-person singular verbal suffix (e.g. <i>ulaşsın</i> “you can reach”)	8	11,11
first-person plural reflexive pronoun (e.g. <i>kendimize</i> “to ourselves”)	4	5,56
first-person plural reflexive pronoun (e.g. <i>kendimizi</i> “ourselves”)	4	5,56
first-person plural verbal suffix with subordinating suffixes and possessive suffixes (e.g. <i>ilgilendiğimiz ...</i> “that we are interested in”)	4	5,56
<i>-(I)nIz</i> , second-person plural possessive suffix (e.g. <i>hedefleriniz</i> “your aims”)	3	4,17
second-person singular pronoun, <i>sen</i> “you”	2	2,78
second-person plural suffix with subordinating suffixes and possessive suffixes (e.g. <i>yaptığımız ...</i> “that you do”)	2	2,78
second-person singular suffix with subordinating suffixes and possessive suffixes (e.g. <i>hayal ettiğin ...</i> “that you dreamed”)	2	2,78
<i>-In(Iz)</i> imperative suffix for second person plural (e.g. <i>Belirleyin!</i> “Determine!”)	2	2,78
<i>-(y)ayIm</i> , imperative suffix first-person optative (e.g. <i>Anlatayım!</i> “Let me tell”)	1	1,38
first-person plural object pronouns (e.g. <i>bizi</i> “us”)	1	1,38
first-person plural reflexive pronoun (e.g. <i>kendimiz</i> “ourselves”)	1	1,38
rhetorical questions (e.g. <i>...nelerdir?</i> “what are (they)?”)	1	1,38
Total	72	100,00

As Table 5 illustrates, the most frequent markers are the first-person plural verbal suffixes (e.g., *yapıyoruz* “we do ...”), accounting for 20,84% of the text. Following closely are the first-person plural possessive suffixes (e.g., *hayallerimiz* “our dreams”), which comprise 16,67% of the text. Other engagement markers appear in various forms, such as first-person plural reflexive pronouns like *kendimizi* “ourselves”, second-person singular possessive pronouns (e.g., *hedeflerin* “your aims”), and second-person plural possessive suffixes (e.g., *hedefleriniz* “your aims”). This suggests that, even if the overall frequency of engagement markers is low, students prefer to engage readers in their texts by using a combination of direct and indirect strategies, creating a more interactive tone. Below is an example of engagement markers in a sentence extracted from the corpus.

(4) *Hayallerimizin peşine gitmek çok önemlidir.* “Chasing **our** dreams is very important.”

The first-person plural possessive suffixes, such as *-(I)mIz* “our”, directly involve readers, encouraging them to see themselves as part of the shared pursuit of dreams and fostering a sense of dialogue in reader interactions.

3.1.5. Hedges

Hedges are the least frequently used interactional markers in Albanian students' opinion texts when writing in L2 Turkish. This demonstrates that students rarely convey uncertainty or caution in their arguments, highlighting the need to express uncertainty or possibilities in academic writing.

Data analysis reveals that hedges appear in the texts through the use of pronouns (e.g., *insan* “human” as a mass noun), epistemic adverbs (e.g., *belki* “perhaps”), epistemic adjectives (e.g., *bazı* “some”), and epistemic modal suffixes (e.g., *-(y)Abil+-(A/I)r* “may PSB-AOR-3SG”). Table 6 presents a list of all occurrences of hedges, along with their frequencies and percentages, in L2 Turkish texts written by Albanian learners.

Table 6

Frequency and Percentages of Hedges in L2 Turkish Opinion Texts

Hedges	Frequency	Percentage (%)
<i>insanlar</i> “people”	9	20,00
<i>insan</i> “human”	8	17,79
<i>bazı</i> “some”	5	11,11
<i>gibi</i> “like”	4	8,89
<i>belki</i> “perhaps”	3	6,67
<i>birkaç</i> “a few”	3	6,67
<i>-dAn biri</i> “one of ...”	3	6,67
<i>bazen</i> “sometimes”	2	4,44
<i>-(y)Abil+-(A/I)r</i> “May PSB-AOR-3SG”	2	4,44
<i>herhangi bir</i> “anything”	1	2,22
<i>biraz</i> “some”	1	2,22
<i>mümkün</i> “possible”	1	2,22
<i>sanki</i> “as if”	1	2,22
<i>genelde</i> “usually”	1	2,22
<i>çoğu</i> “many”	1	2,22
Total	45	100,00

Table 6 shows that Albanian students use a variety of hedges in their L2 Turkish texts, reflecting different levels of caution and specificity in their writing. The most frequently used hedges are *insanlar* “people” and *insan* “human”, which appear 9 and 8 times, respectively. Although these terms are not traditionally classified as hedges, their high frequency suggests that students often generalize or discuss broad categories, potentially softening the specificity of their arguments. Other hedges identified in the corpus, such as *bazı* “some”, *gibi* “like”, *belki* “perhaps”, *birkaç* “a few”, and *-dAn biri* “one of ...” indicate caution, approximation and recognition of uncertainty. The sentence below illustrates an example of a hedge used in the corpus.

- (5) *Bazen pes etmek istiyoruz ama aynı zamanda pes edemiyoruz.* “**Sometimes** we want to give up but at the same time we can't.”

In example (5), *bazen* “sometimes” softens the statement by introducing a degree of uncertainty. This softening effect renders the argument less absolute and more reflective of real-life complexities.

Until now, I have addressed the use of interactional markers in L2 Turkish student opinion texts written by native Albanian students. The findings and discussion will proceed with the use of interactive markers in L2 Turkish texts, starting with the most frequently used ones, presented in descending order.

3.1.6. Transitions

In the corpus of this study, transitions are the most frequently used interactive elements, indicating that students prioritize clear progression in opinion texts.

Data analysis shows that transitions were employed for various functions, such as signalling additive relations (e.g., *ve* “and”), causative relations (e.g., *-mAk için* “in order to”), and contrastive relations between stretches of propositions (e.g., *ama* “but”). This demonstrates the students’ ability to employ a diverse range of connectors to articulate different relationships between ideas. Table 7 displays the frequencies of transitions, ordered from the most to the least frequently used, in L2 Turkish opinion texts written by Albanian students.

Table 7

Frequency and Percentages of Transitions in L2 Turkish Opinion Texts

Transitions	Frequency	Percentage (%)
<i>ve</i> “and”	52	34,21
<i>-mAk için</i> “in order to”	22	14,47
<i>ama</i> “but”	21	13,81
<i>-DiğI için</i> “because”	16	10,52
<i>çünkü</i> “because”	16	10,52
<i>ancak</i> “but”	4	2,63
<i>-(y)Ip</i> “and”	3	1,97
<i>hatta</i> “and”	3	1,97
<i>-mAktAnsA</i> “instead of...”	2	1,32
<i>-In yanısıra</i> “in addition/to”	1	0,66
<i>-mAk adına</i> “in an attempt to”	1	0,66
<i>hem ... hem de</i> “both... and...”	1	0,66
<i>yine de</i> “nevertheless”	1	0,66
<i>madem</i> “since”	1	0,66
<i>bu doğrultuda</i> “accordingly”	1	0,66
<i>ayrıca</i> “also”	1	0,66
<i>-A rağmen</i> “despite...”	1	0,66
<i>yalnızca... değil, aynı zamanda...</i> “not only... but also...”	1	0,66
“... but also...”	1	0,66
<i>-mAklA beraber</i> “as well as ...”	1	0,66
<i>hatta</i> “moreover”	1	0,66
<i>bunun dışında</i> “In addition”	1	0,66
Total	152	100,00

Table 7 illustrates the various transitions employed by Albanian students in their L2 Turkish texts, reflecting their linguistic abilities in strategically establishing logical connections between ideas. *Ve* “and”, for instance, stands out with a frequency of 52, indicating its prevalent use in linking related ideas throughout the texts. This high occurrence suggests its crucial role in maintaining coherence and logical progression, which is essential for guiding readers through complex arguments and discussions. Below is an example of the transitions used in the corpus:

- (6) “*Bu da çoğu insan ilişkilerinin soğuması ve bozulmasına neden oluyor.*” “This also causes many people’s relationships to cool down **and** deteriorate.”

In this sentence, the transition *ve* “and” connects and coordinates two related ideas or actions. It links the cooling and deterioration of relationships as parallel consequences resulting from the same or similar causes. The use of *ve* helps to emphasize that both outcomes, cooling and deterioration of relationships, occur concurrently or as a combined result of multiple factors. This cohesive use of transitions strengthens the logical flow of the sentence, ensuring clarity and coherence in expressing the cause-and-effect relationship within the context of interpersonal dynamics.

Transition markers are essential metadiscoursal devices that facilitate understanding from the reader’s perspective (Basturkmen & Von Randow, 2014; Hyland, 2005) and sustain coherence and logical flow in academic writing. By effectively using transitions, Albanian students can organize their writing more logically and maintain a coherent flow of ideas.

The agglutinative structure of the Turkish language can be viewed as another factor that contributes to the frequent and effective use of transitions by Albanian students, as evidenced by suffixes such as *-Diğl için* “because” and *-mA için* “to...” The adaptation of Albanian students to the Turkish agglutinative structure is noteworthy. This adaptation demonstrates their linguistic flexibility and highlights their ability to leverage the structural features of Turkish to improve their writing and showcase their competence in Turkish academic writing. Similarly, other agglutinative languages, like Finnish and Hungarian, have also been observed to influence the frequent use of transitions in texts, ensuring textual coherence and guiding the reader’s understanding (Kalapos, 2024; Kasik, 1997).

3.1.7. Frame markers

Considering that frame markers organize discourse by guiding readers through the text, signalling sequences, shifting topics, and summarizing points, their relatively low frequency of use with a few realizations may indicate that students are still developing their skills in structuring their writing.

It was found that Albanian students used frame markers to indicate sequence (e.g., *öncelikle* “first of all”), to shift the topic (e.g., *-(y)sA/ise* “as for”), and to label text stages (e.g., *kısacası* “briefly”). Even though these markers are used infrequently, their usage reflects an awareness of the importance of clear text organization, which is essential for effective communication. Table 8 lists the frequencies of frame markers, ordered from the most to the least frequently used, in L2 Turkish opinion texts written by Albanian students.

Table 8

Frequency and Percentages of Frame Markers in L2 Turkish Opinion Texts

Frame markers	Frequency	Percentage (%)
<i>-(y)sA/ise</i> “as for”	7	38,88
<i>ile ilgili</i> “in regard to”	5	27,77
<i>-dAn biri</i> “one of them”	2	11,11
<i>-A dair</i> “about”	1	5,56
<i>kısacası</i> “briefly”	1	5,56

<i>öncelikle</i> “first of all”	1	5,56
<i>konusunda</i> “about”	1	5,56
Total	18	100,00

As shown in Table 8, frame markers such as *-(y)sA/ise* “as for” and *ile ilgili* “regarding” appear most frequently in the corpus. These markers structure and organize information within the text, helping to clarify relationships between ideas, providing context, and guiding the reader through the logical flow of arguments, as in the example below.

(7) *Dünyaya verilecek mesaja gelince, her zaman pozitif düşünmek lazım demek istiyorum.* “As for the message to be conveyed to the world, I want to say that we should always think positively.”

The frame marker *-A gelince* “as for” in *Dünyaya verilecek mesaja gelince* “As for the message to be conveyed to the world”, as seen in example (7), helps transition to a new topic, clarifies the focus, and emphasizes the main point of the discussion.

The use of frame markers in L2 Turkish texts indicates that, while students understand the need for coherence and clarity, the low frequency of their use may be attributed to factors such as limited exposure to advanced writing techniques, a lack of confidence in using such markers effectively, or a greater reliance on alternative methods to achieve coherence, such as transitions.

In texts written in a second language, such as Turkish, mastering frame markers is essential for enhancing coherence and ensuring that complex ideas are conveyed effectively. In other words, these markers are essential for maintaining logical organization in the text, making it easier for readers to follow the writer’s thought process.

3.1.8. Code-glosses

As code-glosses are used less often, it suggests that students may be less willing to provide extra explanations or clarifications of terms and concepts in their writing. This finding could imply that Albanian students writing in L2 Turkish might assume their audience already understands the terms being used or may lack confidence in elaborating on concepts due to language proficiency limitations.

The analysis indicates that students used code-glosses to assist readers in understanding their intended meaning by reformulating it (e.g., *ya da* “or”) and providing examples (e.g., *gibi* “such as”). Table 9 shows the frequencies of code-glosses, listed from most to least frequently used, in L2 Turkish opinion texts written by Albanian students.

Table 9

Frequency and Percentages of Code-glosses in L2 Turkish Opinion Texts

Code-glosses	Frequency	Percentage (%)
<i>ya da</i> “or”	6	35,30
<i>gibi</i> “such as”	3	17,65
<i>the use of paranthesis</i> “()”	3	17,65
<i>yani</i> “in other words”	2	11,76
<i>...diyebiliriz</i> “we can say that...”	1	5,88
<i>örneğin</i> “for example”	1	5,88

<i>mesela</i> “for example”	1	5,88
Total	17	100,00

As shown in Table 9, the frequent use of *ya da* “or” indicates a focus on presenting alternatives. However, the infrequent use of other essential code-glosses such as *örneğin* “for example” and *mesela* “for example” points to a potential area for improvement. This suggests that while Albanian students are proficient at presenting options and adding supplementary details, they could benefit from incorporating more explicit examples and rephrasing to enhance clarity and depth in their academic writing. Below is an example of a code-gloss within a sentence taken from the corpus.

- (8) *Asla evden küs olarak çıkmayın veya kavga ettikten sonra küs uymayın.* “Never leave the house on bad terms **or** stay upset after an argument.”

The code-gloss *veya* “or” in sentence (8) connects two related pieces of advice, providing clarity and emphasizing the importance of not leaving the house upset or remaining upset after an argument. It ensures the reader comprehends the full scope of the guidance being provided. By using code glosses, students attempted to convey their opinions clearly and persuasively, catering to a wider range of readers and their potential interpretations of the text.

3.1.9. Evidentials

Evidentials rank among the least frequently used interactive markers, suggesting that students may struggle to incorporate external evidence into their propositions. The analysis reveals that the only evidential used is *-A göre* “according to” as given in the sentence below.

- (9) *Efsanelere göre, aşk evrendeki en güçlü duygudur.* “**According to legends**, love is the most powerful emotion in the universe.”

The phrase *efsanelere göre* “according to legends”, exemplifies an evidential, which could more appropriately be termed a *metadiscoursal evidential* to distinguish it from the evidential/perfective *-miş* in Turkish. This explicitly states that the information is derived from myths. It indicates that the statement is based on traditional stories or myths rather than on empirical evidence or universally accepted facts.

The infrequent use of metadiscoursal evidentials can be attributed to the genre characteristics of student writing, where the emphasis often lies more on presenting ideas and arguments directly rather than rigorously supporting them with references or external sources. On the other hand, this low frequency indicates a potential challenge in effectively integrating sources into their writing. It may reflect a lack of familiarity with the conventions of citing and referencing sources, or they may not feel the need to refer to an idea that originates from another source outside the text, as this is primarily an opinion-based text. Nonetheless, these resources are not limited to citation forms, particularly those requiring specific information outside the text, such as the author-date format.

According to Yang (2013), there are various types of evidential metadiscourse markers, including lexicogrammatical expressions of reporting evidentials. These can be divided into verbal and non-verbal forms. Verbal markers often appear in structures such as “Author + year” (e.g., Hunston, 2000) or verb-based constructions like “X argues that” or “It is argued

that.” Other forms include passive constructions (e.g., “It has been revealed”) and “as” structures (e.g., “As indicated by...”). Non-verbal markers, on the other hand, consist of noun-based structures such as “fact that”, “observation that” or “claim that” as well as adjunct phrases like “according to X” “in X’s data” or “in X’s view.” Phrases such as “according to the literature”, “according to statistics” or even “according to legend” can also serve as evidentials. Therefore, metadiscoursal evidentials are not limited in a way that would prevent students from using them in opinion-based texts. These markers play a vital role in academic writing by signalling the source and nature of the information presented. They assist readers in interpreting the text accurately, improving the flow of information and making it more accessible and easier to follow.

3.1.10. Endophoric markers

The researcher has not found any instances of endophoric markers in L2 Turkish opinion texts written by Albanian students. Their nonexistence may indicate a different perception of text organization, where such internal references are deemed unnecessary or understood implicitly without the need for specific markers. This suggests a potential area for improvement, as implementing endophoric markers could enhance the text’s coherence by clearly linking various parts of the discourse.

3.2. Comparative Analysis of Interactive and Interactional Categories

This section addresses the second research question by examining whether there is a significant difference in the overall use of interactive and interactional MDMs in the opinion texts of Turkish learners. Table 10 displays the overall frequency (per 100 words) and the log-likelihood results for the total use of interactive and interactional MDMs in the analyzed texts, based on the total corpus size (n= 4,568 words).

Table 10

Overall Frequency (per 100) and Log-likelihood Result of Total Use of Interactive and Interactional MDMs

Metadiscourse	Raw occurrences	F per 100 words	LL ratio
Interactive MDMs	188	4,11	+172,83
Interactional MDMs	534	11,69	

+indicates overuse of interactional MDMs relative to interactive MDMs

As shown in Table 10, interactive MDMs occur 188 times, with a frequency of 4.14 per 100 words, while interactional MDMs appear 534 times, with a frequency of 11.56 per 100 words. The log-likelihood result is +172.83 ($p < 0,0001$), indicating a significant overuse of interactional MDMs compared to interactive ones. This suggests that Albanian students writing in L2 Turkish mainly use metadiscourse to engage the reader while expressing their attitudes and viewpoints, focusing more on content interaction than guiding the reader. This strategy may reflect a more personal and committed writing style, aiming to establish a direct and emotional connection with the audience.

A comparative analysis of interactive and interactional markers has revealed a notable deficiency in interactive markers, apart from transitions. Since these play a crucial role in

enhancing coherence and cohesion in academic writing, the limited use of markers such as frame markers, code glosses, endophoric markers, and evidentials indicates potential for development. Improving students' ability to incorporate these elements could significantly strengthen the logical flow and academic integrity of their work. As shown in Figure 1, the overuse of interactional markers is primarily due to the frequent use of self-mentions. This is followed by attitude markers and boosters; however, hedges and engagement markers are less frequently used. Raising awareness of the importance of consistently applying these markers could motivate students to employ them more regularly, leading to writing that is more engaging and oriented towards the reader. Overall, the findings suggest that teaching approaches should aim to increase students' use of both interactive and interactional markers to improve textual coherence and foster more effective academic writing skills.

Conclusion and Suggestions

This study investigates the role of metadiscourse in L2 Turkish opinion texts written by native Albanian students. By examining both the interactive and interactional aspects of metadiscourse based on Hyland's (2005) Interpersonal Model of Metadiscourse, this research provides a comprehensive examination of how Albanian learners of Turkish utilise these rhetorical devices to structure their opinion writing and engage with readers. The inclusion of nearly all categories within their texts emphasizes the significant role of metadiscourse in their writing.

Both quantitative and qualitative analyses reveal a high frequency of self-mentions and transitions, contrasting with the limited use of evidentials and endophoric markers. The prevalence of self-mentions reflects students' preference for personal engagement in their writing, which helps assert their opinions and strengthen their arguments. Turkish's agglutinative structure facilitates frequent use of self-mentions, as its language-specific nature significantly influences metadiscourse usage (e.g., Gai & Wang, 2022; Kafes, 2017; Zarei & Mansoori, 2011; Zhao & Wu, 2024). Although Albanian is inflected, it shares lexical similarities with agglutinative structures (Camaj, 1984; Newmark et al., 1982), which may affect how Albanian speakers produce metadiscourse in L2 Turkish. Similarly, Albanian students often employ transitions to enhance logical coherence, effectively connecting ideas and indicating relationships, thereby improving the clarity of their writing. The variety of suffixes functioning as transitions arises not only from the Turkish language's agglutinative structure but also from the genre-specific nature of metadiscourse (e.g., Bogdanović, 2014; Kawase, 2015; Kuhi & Mojood, 2014; Obeng et al., 2023). Conversely, the lesser use of evidentials and the absence of endophoric markers in this study could also be attributed to genre-specific characteristics, as opinion text writers do not typically require the extensive citations found in academic writing, such as those generally found in research articles. The results regarding the distribution of MDMs align with Mahmood et al. (2017), who examined genre-based opinion texts and previous L2 Turkish studies (Kurudayıoğlu & Çimen, 2020; Soyşekerçi et al., 2022; Şimşek & Erol, 2023), showing a noticeable dominance of self-mentions and transitions, with fewer evidentials and endophoric markers.

The comparative analysis shows that interactional categories were used significantly more often than interactive categories in L2 Turkish opinion texts written by Albanian students. It is clear from the data that the overuse of interactional markers correlates with the frequent use of self-mentions. These findings align with previous research on L2 writing and metadiscourse. Hyland (2004) observed that L2 writers often use interactional markers to engage with readers, emphasising personal involvement and stance-taking. Zarei and Mansoori (2011) noted that Iranian EFL learners used interactional MDMs more often than interactive markers. These studies consistently indicate that L2 writers tend to prioritise interactional markers, focusing on engaging readers and expressing the writer's stance. The findings of this study suggest that teaching strategies should focus on guiding students to use more interactive markers to enhance coherence in academic writing. In this context, increasing the use of frame markers, code glosses, endophoric markers, and evidentials could significantly improve coherence and the flow of the texts.

The findings reveal that metadiscourse markers in L2 Turkish students' opinion texts are unevenly distributed, with one type predominating. Therefore, it is essential to develop appropriate educational materials to ensure that learners of Turkish for academic purposes are exposed to and can effectively use these markers in both written and spoken communication. Nonetheless, even though some categories have a low frequency, they still show variation. In this context, different realizations of each metadiscourse marker should be included in instruction. For instance, frame markers can be used to announce goals (e.g., *bu metinde* "in this text"), endophoric markers can refer to previous or upcoming parts (e.g., *aşağıda bahsedilecektir* "it will be discussed below" *daha önce belirtildiği gibi* "as previously stated") and attitude markers can convey stance through deontic modal suffixes (e.g., *-mAll* "OBLG"). Similarly, boosters indicate certainty through modal suffixes (e.g., *-mİş+Dir* "PRF-COP-3SG"), while engagement markers directly involve the reader by appealing to shared knowledge (e.g., *...görülmetedir* "it is observed that...") or by using personal asides like parentheses. Furthermore, various realizations of hedges can be employed to soften arguments. These include epistemic lexical verbs (e.g., *varsay-* "to assume"), passive constructions (e.g., *-Il, -In*) and epistemic modal suffixes (e.g., *-(A/I)r* "AOR-3SG", *-Dir* "COP-3SG", *-(y)AcAk+Dir* "FUT-COP-3SG", *-mİş+Dir* "PRF-COP-3SG", *-mİş ol+mAll+Dir* "PRF AUX-OBLG-COP-3SG", *-(y)Abil+-(A/I)r* "PSB-AOR-3SG", *-(I)yor ol+Abil+Ir/IAr* "IMPF AUX-PSB-AOR-3SG/3PL"). Implementing these strategies can lead to a more balanced and effective development of academic discourse skills.

A detailed analysis reveals a complete absence of passive constructions in the students' L2 opinion texts, despite instruction on the Turkish passive structure. This may stem from several factors: passive constructions may pose challenges for Albanian students, as Albanian forms the passive voice with an auxiliary verb and a past participle, differing from Turkish's agglutinative nature. Moreover, since Albanian favours active and reflexive constructions, the passive voice may not be the most natural expression. Additionally, the influence of spoken language could impact this tendency. Conducting a student survey could provide insights into challenges arising from structural differences or other influences. Analyzing L2 Turkish texts by learners from the same first language but different language groups will illuminate how

native languages affect learning. These findings can inform personalized instruction that focuses on specific linguistic features, particularly in discourse organization and metadiscourse strategies.

The study has limitations that must be addressed. The small sample size and focus on a single university restrict the generalizability of the findings. Including a broader participant pool and diverse educational contexts would enhance the understanding of metadiscourse in L2 Turkish writing. Future research could investigate how explicit instruction on metadiscourse affects writing proficiency and explore its application in various writing types, such as expository writing, to compare and contrast strategies. This would provide a broader perspective on metadiscursive features across styles. Further investigation of Turkish texts by a homogeneous group is essential to clarify the cultural or native language impacts on metadiscourse use, indicating the need for customized instruction. Expanding research across different educational settings will improve instructional strategies, ultimately fostering the development of proficient L2 Turkish writers.

This research contributes to the expanding body of literature on L2 metadiscourse and provides valuable pedagogical insights. By fostering metadiscourse awareness, educators can improve students' writing skills and overall communicative competence in Turkish. These findings indicate targeted instructional strategies that help students produce more cohesive and engaging academic texts. Incorporating metadiscourse instruction, educators strengthen students' ability to craft coherent and compelling texts, enhancing their understanding of academic writing in Turkish and their proficiency as L2 learner-writers.

Academic writing courses should focus on metadiscourse training, highlighting both interactive and interactional markers. Practical exercises that encourage a blend of these markers are advisable. Integrating metadiscourse into writing curricula enhances students' understanding of academic discourse conventions in the Turkish language. Additionally, peer reviews, group discussions, and diverse writing exercises facilitate hands-on practice with metadiscourse elements. Providing detailed feedback will help students recognize their strengths and areas needing improvement, thereby enhancing their awareness of academic writing conventions in Turkish.

References

- Ädel, A. (2006). *Metadiscourse in L1 and L2 English*. John Benjamins Publishing Company.
- Ädel, A. (2010). Just to give you kind of a map of where we are going: A taxonomy of metadiscourse in spoken and written academic English. *Nordic Journal of English Studies*, 9(2), 69–97.
- Akbaş, E. (2014). Are they discussing in the same way? Interactional metadiscourse in Turkish writers' texts. In *Occupying niches: Interculturality, cross-culturality and aculturality in academic research* (pp. 119-133). Springer.
- Ak Başoğul, D. ve Can, F. S. (2014). Yabancı dil olarak Türkçe öğrenen Balkanlı öğrencilerin yazılı anlatımda yaptıkları hatalar üzerine tespitler. *Journal of Language and Literature Education*, 2(10), 100-119.

- Alavinia, P., & Zarza, S. (2016). Toward a reappraisal of the role of MD Markers in EFL learners' perception of written texts. *The Journal of Language Learning and Teaching*, 2(2), 1-23.
- Basturkmen, H., & Von Randow, J. (2014). Guiding the reader (or not) to re-create coherence: Observations on postgraduate student writing in an academic argumentative writing task. *Journal of English for Academic Purposes*, 16, 14-22.
- Bax, S., Nakatsuhara, F., & Waller, D. (2019). Researching L2 writers' use of metadiscourse markers at intermediate and advanced levels. *System*, 83, 79-95.
- Bayrakdar, E. ve Dilidüzgün, Ş. (2024). Uluslararası öğrencilerin Türkçe akademik yazma becerilerinin değerlendirilmesine yönelik analitik dereceli puanlama anahtarının geliştirilmesi. *Erzincan Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 26(4), 636-659.
- Bogdanović, V. Ž. (2014). Genre-based Metadiscourse analysis in two ESP textbook. *Facta Universitatis-Linguistics and Literature*, 12(2), 115-124.
- Boylu, E., Güney, E. Z. ve Özyalçın, K. E. (2017). Yanlış çözümleme yaklaşımına göre Türkçeyi yabancı dil olarak öğrenen B1 seviyesi öğrencilerinin yazılı anlatımlarının değerlendirilmesi. *International Journal of Languages' Education and Teaching*, 5(3), 184-202.
- Bunton, D. (1999). The use of higher-level metatext in PhD theses. *English for Specific Purposes*, 18(1), 41-56.
- Burneikaitė, N. (2008). Metadiscourse in linguistics master's theses in English L1 and L2. *Kalbotyra*, 59, 38-47.
- Camaj, M. (1984). *Albanian grammar: With exercises, chrestomathy and glossaries*. Otto Harrassowitz Verlag.
- Castillo-Hajan, B., Hajan, B. H., & Marasigan, A. C. (2019). Construction of second language writer identity in student persuasive essays: A metadiscourse analysis. *Online Submission*, 21, 36-60.
- Cubukcu, F. (2017). Revisiting metadiscourse markers of the language learners in academic writing. *Revista Românească pentru Educație Multidimensională*, 9(2), 36-47.
- Çapar, M. (2014). *A study on interactional metadiscourse markers in research articles* [Published Doctoral dissertation]. Anadolu University.
- Çerçi, A., Derman, S. ve Bardakçı, M. (2016). Yabancı dil olarak Türkçe öğrenen öğrencilerin yazılı anlatımlarına yönelik yanlış çözümlemesi. *Gaziantep Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 15(2), 695-715.
- Dafouz-Milne, E. (2003). *Metadiscourse revisited: A contrastive study of persuasive writing in professional discourse* [Unpublished Doctoral dissertation]. Complutense University of Madrid.

- Dahl, T. (2004). Textual metadiscourse in research articles: A marker of national culture or of academic discipline? *Journal of Pragmatics*, 36(10), 1807-1825.
- Demiriz, H. N. ve Okur, A. (2019). Türkçe öğretiminde yazma öğretimine akademik Türkçe aşamasında yabancı öğrenciler üzerinden bir bakış. *Ana Dili Eğitimi Dergisi*, 7(2), 436-449.
- Ebrahimi, S. J. (2018). The role of metadiscourse markers in comprehending texts of reading comprehension books published in Iran and oxford university press. *International Journal of Applied Linguistics and English Literature*, 7(3), 90-96.
- Eghtesadi, A. R., & Navidinia, H. (2009). A comparative study of metadiscourse use in research articles written by native and non-native speakers: Is audience taken into account?. *Journal of Asia TEFL*, 6(3), 157-176.
- Esmer, E. (2018). Türkçeyi yabancı dil olarak öğrenen öğrenciler tarafından üretilen ikna metinlerinde üstsöylem belirleyicilerinin kullanımı. *Dil Eğitimi ve Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 4(3), 216-228.
- Gai, F. H., & Wang, Y. (2022). Correlated metadiscourse and metacognition in writing research articles: A cross-linguistic and cross-cultural study. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 1026554.
- Guziurová, T. (2017). The role of metadiscourse in genre analysis: Engagement markers in undergraduate textbooks and research articles. *Contrastive Analysis of Discourse-pragmatic Aspects of Linguistic Genres*, 211-233.
- Güler, E. B. ve Eyüp, B. (2016). Hâl eklerinin ikinci dil olarak Türkçe öğrenen öğrenciler tarafından kullanılması. *Electronic Turkish Studies*, 11(14).
- Hawkey, R., & Barker, F. (2004). Developing a common scale for the assessment of writing. *Assessing Writing*, 9(2), 122-159.
- Hunston, S. (2000). Evaluation and planes of discourse: Status and value in persuasive texts. In S. Hunston & G. Francis (Eds.), *Pattern grammar: A corpus-driven approach to lexical grammar of English*. Benjamins.
- Hyland, K. (1996). Talking to academy: Forms of hedging in science research articles. *Written Communication*, 13(2), 251-82.
- Hyland, K. (2000). *Disciplinary discourses: Social interactions in academic writing*. Longman.
- Hyland, K. (2004). Disciplinary interactions: Metadiscourse in L2 postgraduate writing. *Journal of Second Language Writing*, 13(2), 133-151.
- Hyland, K. (2005). *Metadiscourse: Exploring interaction in writing*. Continuum.
- Hyland, K. (2008). Persuasion, interaction and the construction of knowledge: representing self and others in research writing. *IJES*, 8 (2), 1-23.

- Hyland, K., & Tse, P. (2004). Metadiscourse in academic writing: A reappraisal. *Applied Linguistics*, 25(2), 156-177.
- Ingebrand, S. W. (2016). *The development of writing skills: The use of genre-specific elements in second and third grade students' writing* [Published doctoral dissertation]. Arizona State University.
- Intaraprawat, P., & Steffensen, M. S. (1995). The use of metadiscourse in good and poor ESL essays. *Journal of Second Language Writing*, 4(3), 253-272.
- Junqueira, L., & Cortes, V. (2014). Metadiscourse in book reviews in English and Brazilian Portuguese: A corpus-based analysis. *Journal of Rhetoric, Professional Communication, and Globalization*, 6(1), 5.
- Kafes, H. (2017). An intercultural investigation of meta-discourse features in research articles by American and Turkish academic writers. *International Journal of Languages' Education and Teaching*, 5(3), 373-391.
- Kalapos, A. (2024). *On the syntax-morphology divide: Towards a unified analysis of causatives. The case of Hungarian and Japanese* [Published doctoral dissertation]. Concordia University.
- Karimi, K., Maleki, M., & Farnia, M. (2017). Metadiscourse markers in the abstract sections of Persian and English law articles. *International Journal of Foreign Language Teaching and Research*, 5(18), 69-83.
- Kartallıoğlu, N. ve Topuzkanamış, E. (2021). Bir yanlış çözümlemesi araştırması: Yabancı öğrenciler neyi yanlış yazıyor? *RumeliDE Dil ve Edebiyat Araştırmaları Dergisi*, (25), 38-55.
- Kasik, R. (1997). Typology of Estonian and Finnish word-formation: The verb. *Estonian: Typological Studies*, 2, 42-73.
- Kawase, T. (2015). Metadiscourse in the introductions of PhD theses and research articles. *Journal of English for Academic Purposes*, 20, 114-124.
- Koleci, F & Turano, G. (2011). *Introduction to generative syntax*. Publishing House of the University Book.
- Kondowe, W. (2014). Hedging and boosting as interactional metadiscourse in literature doctoral dissertation abstracts. *International Journal of Language Learning and Applied Linguistics World*, 5(3), 214-221.
- Köroğlu, Z. (2018). A study on metadiscursive interaction in the doctoral dissertations of the native speakers of English and the Turkish speakers of English. *Journal of Language and Linguistic Studies*, 14(3), 396-404.
- Kuhi, D., & Mojood, M. (2014). Metadiscourse in newspaper genre: A cross-linguistic study of English and Persian editorials. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 98, 1046-1055.

- Kurudayıoğlu, M. ve Çimen, L. (2020). Yabancı dil olarak Türkçe öğrenen öğrencilerin akademik yazılarında etkileşimli üstsöylem belirleyicilerinin kullanımı. *OPUS International Journal of Society Researches*, 16(31), 3899-3923.
- Lee, J. J., & Deakin, L. (2016). Interactions in L1 and L2 undergraduate student writing: Interactional metadiscourse in successful and less-successful argumentative essays. *Journal of Second Language Writing*, 33, 21-34.
- Letsoela, P.M. (2014). Interacting with readers: Metadiscourse features in national university of Lesotho undergraduate students' academic writing. *International Journal of Linguistics*, 5(6), 138-153.
- Mahmood, R., Javaid, G., & Mahmood, A. (2017). Analysis of metadiscourse features in argumentative writing by Pakistani undergraduate students. *International Journal of English Linguistics*, 7(6), 78-87.
- Mauranen, A. (1993). *Cultural differences in academic rhetoric: A textlinguistic study*. Peter Lang.
- Newmark, L., Hubbard, P., & Prifti, P. R. (1982). *Standard Albanian: A reference grammar for students*. Stanford University Press.
- Obeng, B., Wornyo, A. A., & Hammond, C. (2023). Variations in rhetorical moves and metadiscourse elements in conference abstracts: A genre analysis. *European Journal of Applied Linguistics Studies*, 6(1).
- Oshima, A., & Hogue, A. (1988). *Introduction to academic writing*. Addison-Wesley Publishing Company.
- Ozdemir, N. O., & Longo, B. (2014). Metadiscourse use in thesis abstracts: A cross-cultural study. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 141, 59-63.
- Seyedi, G. (2019). *Yabancı dil olarak Türkçe öğretiminde akademik yazma öğretimi* [Unpublished dissertation]. Hacettepe University.
- Simin, S. & Tavangar, M. (2009). Metadiscourse knowledge and use in Iranian EFL writing. *Asian EFL Journal*, 11(1), 230-255.
- Soyşekerci, G., Öztürk, E. A. ve İşeri, K. (2022). Lisansüstü tezlerin sonuç bölümlerinde üstsöylem belirleyicileri. *Çukurova Üniversitesi Türkoloji Araştırmaları Dergisi*, 7(2), 766-794.
- Swales, J. M., & Feak, C. B. (2004). *Academic writing for graduate students: Essential tasks and skills* (Vol. 1). University of Michigan Press.
- Şimşek, R., & Erol, T. (2023). Akademik Türkçe içeriklerinde üstsöylem belirleyicilerin görünümleri. *Kahramanmaraş Sütçü İmam Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 20(2), 393-403.
- Vande Kopple, W. J. (2012). The importance of studying metadiscourse. *Applied Research on English Language*, 1(2), 37-44.

- Vázquez Orta, I., & Giner, D. (2009). Writing with conviction: The use of boosters in modelling persuasion in academic discourses. *Revista Alicantina de Estudios Ingleses* 22, 219-237.
- Williams, J. M. (1982). *Style: Ten lessons in clarity and grace*. Scott, Foresman.
- Yağmur Şahin, E., İşcan, A., Kana, F. ve Koçer, Ö. (2013). Yabancı dil olarak Türkçe öğrenen öğrencilerin ihtiyaç algıları: Betimsel bir durum çalışması. *The Journal of Academic Social Science Studies*, 6(4), 1185-1119.
- Yang, L. (2013). Evaluative functions of reporting evidentials in English research articles of applied linguistics. *Open Journal of Modern Linguistics*, 3(2), 119-126.
- Zarei, G. R., & Mansoori, S. (2011). A contrastive study on metadiscourse elements used in humanities vs. non humanities across Persian and English. *English Language Teaching*, 4(1), 42-50.
- Zhao, C. G., & Wu, J. (2024). Voice and voicing strategies across native and second language writing: Extending the interactional metadiscourse framework. *Applied Linguistics*, 45(6), 1075-1090.

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Genişletilmiş Özet

Üstsöylem belirleyicileri (ing. metadiscourse markers), metin içinde yazarın düşüncelerini ve iddialarını düzenlemesine yardımcı olan unsurlardır ve akademik yazımda önemli bir rol oynar. Bu çalışma, ana dili Arnavutça olan öğrenciler tarafından yazılan D2 Türkçe görüş denemelerinde üstsöylem belirleyicilerinin kullanımını araştırmaktadır. Çalışma sonuçlarının ikinci dildeki akademik yazmalarda üstsöylemin rolünü derinleştirerek etkili dil öğrenme stratejilerine katkıda bulunması beklenmektedir.

Bu çalışmanın amacı, Türkçeyi ikinci yabancı dil olarak öğrenen ve ana dili Arnavutça olan öğrencilerin kullandıkları üstsöylem belirleyicilerini detaylı bir şekilde tanımlamak, alıcı odaklı etkileşimli üstsöylem ulamları (ing. interactional metadiscourse categories) ve bilgi odaklı etkileşimli üstsöylem ulamları (ing. interactive metadiscourse categories) arasında anlamlı bir fark olup olmadığını ortaya çıkarmaktır. Araştırmanın yanıtlamayı hedeflediği iki temel soru şu şekildedir:

Ana dili Arnavutça olan öğrenciler tarafından yazılan D2 Türkçe görüş yazılarında;

1. Kullanılan üstsöylem belirleyicileri ve bu belirleyicilerin kullanım sıklıkları neledir?
2. Alıcı odaklı etkileşimli ve bilgi odaklı etkileşimli üstsöylem belirleyicilerinin genel kullanım sıklıkları arasında anlamlı bir fark var mıdır?

Araştırma, Priştine Üniversitesinde öğrenim gören, B2-C1 seviyelerinde Türkçe bilen ve ana dili Arnavutça olan 30 öğrenciyi kapsamaktadır. Veri toplama aşamasında öğretmenlerin yardımıyla uygunluk örnekleme yöntemi uygulanmıştır. Öğrencilerden, “Dünyaya bir mesaj verecek olsaydınız, bu ne olurdu?” konulu en az 170 kelimelik görüş denemeleri yazmaları istenmiştir. Bu tür denemeler, öğrencilere kendi görüş ve fikirlerini ifade etme, bunları ikna edici biçimde destekleme ve yazılı iletişim becerilerini geliştirme fırsatı sunmaktadır.

Toplanan metinlerdeki toplam sözcük sayısı 4,568’dir. Veri çözümlemesi hem nicel hem de nitel yöntemleri içeren karma bir yaklaşım kullanılarak yapılmıştır. Çözümleme, Hyland’ın (2005) “Kişilerarası Üstsöylem Modeli” çerçevesinde gerçekleştirilmiş olup alıcı odaklı etkileşimli ve bilgi odaklı etkileşimli üstsöylem belirleyicileri detaylı bir şekilde incelenmiştir. Ayrıca, AntConc 4.2.0 yazılımı ve Log-olabilirlik (ing. Log-likelihood) oran istatistiği kullanılmıştır.

Sonuçlar, ana dili Arnavutça olan öğrencilerin D2 Türkçe görüş denemelerinde üstsöylem belirleyicilerini oldukça çeşitli şekillerde kullandıklarını ortaya koymaktadır. Toplamda 722 üstsöylem belirleyicisi kullanılması, metinlerin yüzde 15,8’ini oluşturarak önemli bir yer tuttuğunu göstermektedir.

Alıcı odaklı etkileşimli üstsöylem ulamları arasında kendinden söz etme (ing. self-mention) yüzde 26,49’luk oranla en yaygın kullanılan belirleyicidir. Bu durum, yazarın kişisel görüşlerini ve metne olan katılımını belirgin bir şekilde ifade ettiğini gösterir. Tutum belirleyicileri (ing. attitude markers) yüzde 17,99, vurgulayıcılar (ing. boosters) ise yüzde 13,94 oranında kullanılmıştır. Bu oranlar, öğrencilerin iddialarının gücünü ve kişisel görüşlerini vurgulama çabalarını yansıtır. Katılım belirleyicileri (ing. engagement markers) (Yüzde 8,92) okuyucuyu metin içine doğrudan dâhil etme çabalarını göstermektedir. Kaçınmalar (ing. hedges) ise yüzde 6,27’lik oranıyla daha az sıklıkta kullanılmıştır. Bu da öğrencilerin ifadelerinde genellikle kendinden emin olduğunu gösterir.

Mantıksal bağlayıcılar (ing. transitions) yüzde 21,05’lük oranla en sık kullanılan bilgi odaklı etkileşimli ulamlar arasında yer almaktadır. Bu, öğrencilerin argümanlarının mantıklı bir şekilde akışını sağlama çabalarını ve metinlerin organizasyonuna verdikleri önemi yansıtır. Mantıksal bağlayıcılar, metinlerde düşünceler arasında pürüzsüz bir geçiş sağlayarak okuyucunun yazının akışını takip etmesini kolaylaştırır. Öğrenciler, metinlerin belirli bölümlerini düzenlemek için kullanılan çerçeve belirleyicileri (ing. frame markers), belirsiz ifadeleri açıklığa kavuşturmak için kullanılan açılımlayıcıları (ing. code-glosses) ve bilginin kaynağını göstermek için kullanılan tanıtlayıcıları (ing. evidentials) nadiren (%6’nın altında) kullanmışlardır. Metin içi belirleyicilerin (ing. endophoric markers) kullanımına ise rastlanmamıştır. Bu bulgular, öğrencilerin görüşlerini destekleme ve göndermeleri bağlama konusunda zorluk yaşadığını gösterebilir. Tanıtlayıcılar, görüşlerin desteklenmesi ve metin

uyumunun sağlanması açısından önemli bir rol oynar. Bu nedenle, bu belirleyicilerin daha etkili bir şekilde kullanımı, öğrencilerin akademik yazım becerilerini geliştirebilir.

Bilgi odaklı etkileşimli üstsöylem belirleyicileri ve alıcı odaklı etkileşimli üstsöylem belirleyicilerinin genel sıklığı karşılaştırıldığında, alıcı odaklı etkileşimli üstsöylem belirleyicilerin anlamlı olarak daha fazla kullanıldığı görülmektedir (Log-olabilirlik oranı: +172,83 ($p < 0,0001$)). Bu bulgu, öğrencilerin metinlerinde okuyucularla aktif bir etkileşim kurma eğiliminde olduklarını göstermektedir.

Ana dili Arnavutça olan öğrencilerin üstsöylem belirleyicilerini kullanma biçimlerinin, hem Türkçe hem de Arnavutça dil özelliklerinden etkilendiği söylenebilir. Özellikle, tanımlayıcı ve metin içi belirleyicilerin düşük kullanımı, öğrencilerin bu alanlarda gelişime ihtiyaç duyduğunu gösterir. Tanımlayıcı ve metin içi belirleyicilerinin etkili kullanımı, görüşlerin desteklenmesi ve metin uyumunun sağlanması açısından önemlidir.

Araştırmanın sınırlılıkları arasında küçük örneklem boyutu ve tek bir üniversiteye odaklanması bulunmaktadır. Bu nedenle, daha geniş bir katılımcı grubunu ve çeşitli eğitim bağlamlarını içeren araştırmalar yapılması gerekmektedir. Genişletilmiş örneklem ve farklı bağlamlar, üstsöylem belirleyicileriyle ilgili daha genel ve kapsamlı sonuçlar elde edilmesine olanak tanıyabilir. Ayrıca, farklı dil seviyeleri ve çeşitli akademik bağlamlarda yapılan araştırmalar, öğrencilerin üstsöylem belirleyicileri nasıl kullandıkları hakkında daha derinlemesine bilgi sağlayabilir.

Bu çalışma, öğretim uygulamaları açısından önemli sonuçlar ortaya koymaktadır. Çalışmada üstsöylem belirleyicilerinin, bilhassa bilgi odaklı etkileşimli belirleyicilerin, etkili bir biçimde öğretilmesinin gerekliliği ortaya konmaktadır. Eğitimcilerin bu belirleyicileri öğretme konusundaki farkındalıkları, öğrencilerin yazım performansını ve iletişimsel yeterliliklerini artırabilir. Öğrencilerin üstsöylem belirleyicilerini etkili bir şekilde kullanmaları, akademik yazma becerilerinin geliştirilmesine ve daha etkili iletişim kurmalarına yardımcı olabilir. Bu bulgular, müfredat geliştirme ve akademik yazma becerilerinin iyileştirilmesi için hedeflenmiş pedagojik stratejiler sunmaktadır. Eğitimcilerin üstsöylem belirleyicileri konusunda daha fazla bilgi edinmeleri, öğrencilerin yazılı iletişim becerilerini güçlendirebilir ve akademik başarılarını artırabilir.

Elde edilen bulgular, müfredat geliştirme ve akademik yazma becerilerinin iyileştirilmesine yönelik pedagojik stratejiler açısından önemli katkılar sunmaktadır. Özellikle, bilgi odaklı etkileşimli üstsöylem belirleyicilerinin etkili bir şekilde öğretilmesi gerektiği ortaya çıkmıştır. Eğitimcilerin bu belirleyicileri öğretme konusundaki farkındalığı, öğrencilerin yazma becerilerini ve iletişim yetkinliklerini geliştirebilir. Dolayısıyla, öğrencilerin üstsöylem belirleyicilerini doğru ve etkili kullanmaları, akademik yazma becerilerini güçlendirmelerine ve daha etkili iletişim kurmalarına katkı sağlayabilir. Eğitimcilerin üstsöylem belirleyicileri konusunda daha bilinçli olmaları, öğrencilerin yazılı iletişim becerilerini destekleyerek akademik başarılarını artırabilir.